

IPBES VA Chapter 2. Analysis of national and international policy documents related to biodiversity and sustainability / IPBES values assessment (2.6)

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Description

This review corresponds to the IPBES values assessment. To provide insights into how different environmental and development policies relate to the concepts assessed in chapter 2, we selected broad policy 'domains' associated with international environmental governance. First, we sought to include representation of assessments prepared by the Intergovernmental Platform for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) and the National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) reported by countries from the Global North and South to the Convention for Biological Diversity (CBD). We also used the two core documents related to the UN Agenda 2030 Agenda for Sustainability and the Sustainable Development Goals. Then, we incorporated major global reports on biodiversity (World Wildlife Fund) and economics and ecosystem services (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, The Economics

of Ecosystems and Biodiversity, Dasgupta Review). We also considered two regional environmental agreements from the Global North and South (European Union, Latin American and the Caribbean). Finally, to ensure a sectoral perspective, we also assessed reports from the UN Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO). This literature review is part of chapter 2 stage 2 strategy intended to encompass different sources of evidence appropriate for each section and subsection.

Process overview

Protocol

- **Type of review:** Systematic review of national and international policy documents
- **Search languages:** English and Spanish
- **Search details:** as described in (R1)
- **Search date:** June 2020
- **Sample extracted:** 39 policy documents
- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - Publication title
 - Year of publication
 - What level is this document (National, International)
- **Location and format of the data (A):** IPBES_VA_2.6_07-2020_(A).csv

Treatment applied: policy documents were coded using 22 codes as specified in **(R2)**.

Results and analysis are presented throughout *chapter 2* and in *annex 2.2*.

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA_2.6_07-2020_(A)	csv	3 KB	39 policy documents selected for this literature review
R1	IPBES_VA_2.6_06-2020_(R1)	pdf	142 KB	Criteria to select policy documents for the literature review
R2	IPBES_VA_2.6_07-2020_(R2)	pdf	129 KB	Criteria and codes for reviewing the policy documents in (A)